

Seeing Danger Before It Happens: Challenges in Developing Data-Driven In-Vehicle Hazard Warning Systems

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Abstract. Data holds significant promise for enabling advanced, data-driven services, including in-vehicle hazard warning systems. As data spaces and data ecosystems continue to mature, the availability of relevant data assets for such applications is expected to increase substantially. This paper reviews the current state of driver warning systems and presents findings from a research project that developed a prototypical data-driven in-vehicle hazard warning system designed to alert drivers to potential dangers along their route. We describe the system’s architectural design and implementation, presenting our implementation approach and the developed system prototype, and discuss the key challenges encountered during its prototypical development. These challenges span backend processing and event generation, frontend design and warning mechanisms, the availability and integration of warning-relevant data, and the transformation of heterogeneous data sources into actionable warnings. Additional challenges include defining warning logic through expert-developed scenarios, handling data validity and expiration to ensure timely and reliable alerts and addressing human factors such as warning modality and user acceptance. By systematically examining these challenges and presenting our implementation approach and the developed system prototype, this paper contributes to a deeper understanding of the technical and systemic requirements for building dependable, data-driven in-vehicle hazard warning applications within an evolving mobility data ecosystem.

Keywords: Data-driven services, driver warning systems, in-vehicle hazard alerts, geospatial event processing, risk modelling.

1 Introduction and Motivation First Section

The rapid digitalization of the mobility and transport ecosystem is generating an ever-growing volume of data (Möller et al. 2024), which has become a valuable asset for a wide range of stakeholders. This data holds significant potential for enabling data-driven services (Zambetti et al. 2021), opening new avenues for innovation and value creation (Stocker et al. 2024).

At the same time, the automotive industry is undergoing a paradigm shift—from viewing vehicles as isolated products to recognizing them as integral components of a

broader, connected ecosystem (Nischak and Hanelt 2019). This shift supports the emergence of data-driven business models centered on connected and software-defined vehicles (Sterk et al. 2024; Otto et al. 2025). By combining vehicle data with contextual information, novel data-driven services such as driver warning systems can be developed to deliver value to end users (Kaiser et al. 2021), particularly when integrated into vehicle information systems directly accessible to drivers (Kaiser et al. 2018).

Driver warning systems (Driver et al. 2021) represent a subclass of advanced driver assistance systems (ADAS) and encompass a broad range of functionalities. These include collision warning, lane departure warning, blind spot detection, driver drowsiness and attention monitoring (cf. Kashevnik et al. 2021), speed limit and traffic sign recognition, pedestrian and cyclist warnings, as well as hazard warnings.

The primary objective of these systems is to enhance driving safety and improve drivers' situational awareness (Schömig and Metz 2013) by providing timely and contextually relevant alerts about potential risks and critical driving conditions.

In this paper, we focus on hazard warning systems (Xu et al. 2024; Ryder et al. 2016), a specific category of driver warning systems aimed at alerting drivers to potential or emerging dangers along their route and within their driving environment. Our objective is to design and implement a system capable of delivering timely hazard warnings based on data shared by external sources and the extraction of risk-relevant information.

Such data may include weather conditions, signals from other vehicles (e.g., indications of distracted driving or activation of electronic stability control due to slippery road conditions), and contextual information such as accident hotspots. We report on our experiences in developing a data-driven, in-vehicle hazard warning system, presenting its architectural design and analyzing the key challenges encountered during implementation.

Despite the increasing trend toward automated driving (Ebinger et al. 2024), there remains a strong—and arguably growing—need for driver warning systems (European Commission 2025), as human drivers will continue to bear responsibility for driving tasks in passenger vehicles for the foreseeable future (Stocker 2025). Moreover, trust is a critical prerequisite for the adoption and effective use of data- and AI-based systems (Stocker et al. 2025). Against this background, we consider this paper a valuable contribution to the ongoing development of data-driven hazard warning systems, offering insights relevant to researchers, developers, and practitioners alike.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Following the introduction and motivation in Section 1, Section 2 reviews the state of the art in hazard-based driver warning systems. Section 3 presents the proposed approach and system architecture, while Section 4 discusses the application challenges encountered. Section 5 reports on the developed system prototype and outlines the limitations of the study. Finally, Section 6 concludes with an outlook on future research directions.

Finally, we note that this paper is an extended version of the work by Stocker and Musser (2025) presented at the WEBIST 2025 conference.

2 Related Work

2.1 Driver Warning Systems

The human driver is still a central factor in road safety and, regrettably, remains the leading cause of accidents. Human errors such as speeding and other bad driving styles (Sagberg et al., 2015, Kaiser et al. 2020) distraction and inattention (Regan et al. 2011), misjudgment and driving errors (Paker et al. 1995) contribute significantly to traffic incidents. Driver warning systems aim to reduce these risks by delivering timely alerts that enhance the driver's situational awareness and support safer decision-making on the road.

Driver warning systems represent a subclass of driver assistance systems (Bengler et al. 2014) and encompass a wide range of functionalities aimed at enhancing driving safety by alerting the driver to potential hazards or critical driving conditions. These systems are designed to support drivers in maintaining awareness and to help prevent accidents by providing timely warnings, rather than taking direct control of the vehicle. Common examples include collision warnings (Jameson et al., 2008), which alert the driver when a crash is imminent, lane departure warnings (Chen et al., 2020), which detect unintentional drifting out of the lane, and blind spot detection systems (Liu et al. 2017), which monitor adjacent lanes for unseen vehicles during lane changes. Driver drowsiness and attention monitoring systems (cf. Kashevnik et al., 2021) assess driver behaviour and alertness to detect signs of fatigue or distraction. Other functionalities include speed limit and traffic sign recognition systems, which inform the driver of relevant road signs, and pedestrian or cyclist warnings, which help identify vulnerable road users in the vehicle's path.

One particularly important category is hazard warning systems (Xu et al. 2024, Ryder et al. 2016), which aim to alert the driver to unexpected or evolving dangers, such as slippery roads, stationary vehicles, road obstructions, or accident hotspots (Ryder et al. 2016), especially those that may lie beyond the range of the vehicle's onboard sensors. Unlike traditional systems that rely solely on local perception through in-vehicle sensors, hazard warning systems increasingly leverage external data sources, such as information shared by other vehicles, by the infrastructure, or by cloud-based data services. This allows for broader situation awareness and earlier warnings, enabling drivers to react proactively to potential risks that would otherwise go undetected until the last moment. By integrating vehicle and contextual data (Kaiser et al. 2018, Stocker et al. 2013), hazard warning systems can significantly enhance driving safety, particularly in complex or dynamic traffic environments.

2.2 Factors Influencing Driving Safety

Several factors influence driving safety, and they can generally be grouped into three main categories: individual factors, route-related factors, and environmental factors. Individual factors relate to the driver's personal state (Regan et al. 2011) and behavior (Sagberg et al., 2015). Key aspects include attention and distraction levels (for example, using a phone while driving), fatigue or drowsiness (Young et al., 2007), driving experience and skill, emotional state (such as stress or anger), any physical impairments

(like the influence of alcohol or medication), and general driving behavior (such as speeding or aggressive maneuvers).

Route-related factors (Intini et al. 2019; Bogenreif et al. 2012) concern the specific characteristics of the route ahead. Examples include road layout (like curves or intersections), the condition of the road surface, traffic density, known accident-prone areas, and the presence or quality of road signs and markings. Temporary conditions like road-works or obstacles can also affect safety.

Environmental Factors refer to external conditions that can impact driving (Maze et al. 2006; Malin et al. 2019). Common examples include weather conditions (rain, fog, ice), lighting (daylight, darkness, glare), visibility, and the presence of other road users such as pedestrians or cyclists. Unexpected events like accidents or emergency vehicles also fall into this category.

Fig. 1. Individual factors for driving safety.

Human behavior on the road is a dominant factor in accidents, accounting for over 70% of incidents (McCarty & Kim, 2024). Actions by other road users such as speeding, aggressive maneuvers, or collision involvement present substantial risks and can directly precipitate crashes (Osafune et al., 2017). Young drivers (ages 16–25) face an elevated risk of casualty accidents compared to older cohorts, a disparity largely driven by their higher propensity for risk-taking behind the wheel (Jonah, 1986). To better understand these variations, Sagberg et al. (2015) propose a comprehensive framework for categorizing and operationalizing driving styles in relation to risk.

The impact of weather, e.g., wind, temperature, and rain, on traffic accidents has been acknowledged by many researchers. Maze et al. (2006) showed that harsh weather conditions such as snowstorms increase traffic accident risks significantly. The underlying factors were found to be especially low visibility and wind. Furthermore, the study concludes that weather also significantly impacts speed and traffic volume.

Bergel-Hayat et al. (2013) found correlations between rainfall/temperature and traffic accidents. In another study, Malin et al. (2019) considered slippery roads and poor visibility important factors correlating with accident risk. It should be noted that in some data sets, e.g., as studied by Theofilatos (2017), weather is not necessarily a relevant factor for accident likelihood or severity.

Apart from weather conditions, road geometry is another critical factor influencing traffic accidents. Road geometry encompasses characteristics such as road curvature, the number of lanes, and the width of lanes and shoulders. For instance, Karlaftis and Golias (2002) found that when accident data is normalized, variables such as lane width, pavement condition, and access control become significant predictors. Their study also revealed that the importance of lane width increases with higher traffic volumes, while pavement type becomes less influential due to reduced speeds. Similarly, Rengarasu et al. (2009) demonstrated that lane width, in combination with other factors and adjacent road segments, impacts accident rates. The presence of tunnels and bridges was also shown to significantly influence crash risk. Turner and Tate (2009) further analyzed how road geometry affects driver speed choices and, consequently, accident likelihood. In addition, road curvature, often referred to as bendiness, is frequently considered (Bogenreif et al. 2012), too. Dantas et al. (2007), for example, investigated how curvy road segments are associated with increased accident risk.

3 System Architecture and Approach

In this section, we present the architecture of our in-vehicle, data-driven hazard warning system (figure 2 and figure 3) designed to alert drivers to potential dangers. We describe our system’s key components and underlying functional principles. Our system architecture follows a generic, technology-agnostic design to ensure broad applicability and flexibility across different deployment environments. This high-level overview is then followed by a detailed discussion of the implementation challenges encountered, as well as specific technological decisions made during the development of our prototype, in Section 4.

Fig. 2. System Architecture

The basic functional principle of the data-driven in-vehicle hazard warning system is as follows. An in-vehicle client, acting as the edge component of the hazard warning system computes a Geo-Spatial Key (GSK) based on the vehicle's current position and speed. This GSK is transmitted to the central hazard warning platform, which uses it to query relevant internal and external data sources for safety-critical information and events within the defined geographic area and, depending on the event type, relevant timeframes.

The platform processes the collected data by cleaning, consolidating, merging, and enriching it. The complete set of enriched events is transmitted back to the in-vehicle client. The client continuously monitors the vehicle's real-time driving conditions, such as position, speed, and heading, and compares them against the event data received. If it determines that the vehicle is approaching a hazardous event under risky driving conditions, it triggers a warning, which may also reflect the driver's individual preferences such as activating or deactivating certain types of warnings. As the vehicle approaches the boundary of the current GSK region, a new GSK is generated, and the cycle begins anew.

The following sections present each component of the system architecture (Figure 2) and explain its specific role within the overall system. In addition, a sequence diagram (Figure 3) illustrates the procedural flow and interaction between components from a runtime perspective.

3.1 In-Vehicle Client

An in-vehicle client, such as a smartphone with appropriate communication and interaction capabilities or an application embedded in the vehicle's infotainment system, serves as the driver's interface to the data-driven hazard warning platform. It fulfils three primary functions.

First, it provides the user interface through which drivers can log in, configure warning event types and warning mode (e.g. visual only, acoustic only, both), and manage connectivity. It also serves as the output channel for warnings, which may be delivered visually, acoustically, or haptically when a hazard is detected.

Second, the client acts as an edge-computing node, continuously evaluating the events received from the hazard warning platform against real-time driving conditions such as speed and driving direction to determine whether a warning should be issued.

Third, the in-vehicle client can act as a data source itself, sending safety-relevant events or issued warnings back to the platform, contributing to the aggregation, analysis, and refinement of driving risk models.

3.2 Data Source and Data Topic

A data source refers to any device or service that provides safety-relevant information. This can include sensor measurements from in-vehicle clients, hazard-related data shared by other vehicles, weather data from third-party providers, or accident hotspot statistics from governmental agencies.

While these sources deliver critical input for hazard warnings, they typically operate outside the core platform and may involve data access costs, making it important to minimize the number and frequency of data requests. Furthermore, since data sources may emerge, change, or become obsolete over time, the platform must be designed with sufficient flexibility to integrate new feeds or retire outdated ones efficiently.

A data topic, by contrast, is a logical grouping of thematically related data sources, for example, all feeds that provide weather information. Data topics serve as conceptual abstractions that simplify the platform's handling of multiple data sources covering the same subject area. Although not concrete components of the architecture, data topics facilitate more streamlined management, querying, and aggregation of related data feeds.

Fig. 3. Sequence Diagram

3.3 Data Service

A data service encapsulates a single data topic and provides a unified interface to all its underlying sources. For each data topic, there is exactly one corresponding data service, making it a core architectural component of the platform. When queried using a Geo-Spatial Key (GSK), the data service returns a collection of relevant events from its topic. To support these queries efficiently, the data service typically re-indexes incoming data and merges overlapping or redundant information from multiple feeds into a consistent, coherent view.

Beyond query handling, it maintains its own caching layer, persisting incoming data, such as weather conditions, locally according to configurable policies. This not only reduces the need for repeated external data calls (which may incur cost or latency) but also significantly improves response times. By normalizing, deduplicating, and caching topic-specific feeds, the data service abstracts away the complexity of heterogeneous

source formats and variable availability. As a result, higher-level platform components can access harmonized and up-to-date data without dealing directly with the idiosyncrasies of the original data sources.

3.4 Situational Inference and Event Computation Service

The Situational Inference and Event Computation Service is the core component of the system, responsible for assembling and refining the complete set of relevant events for a given Geo-Spatial Key (GSK). Upon invocation, it queries all available data services to retrieve their respective collections of events within the specified GSK region. Each data service is assumed to have already resolved any internal (intra-topic) inconsistencies.

The inference service then reconciles potential conflicts across topics, producing a unified, conflict-free event dataset. It subsequently applies expert-defined rules to infer additional risk-relevant events and to enrich existing ones.

For example, a curve event indicating a sharp bend with a low radius may become significantly more hazardous under adverse weather conditions such as rain or snow. In such cases, the service merges the curve and weather data, generating a composite event that includes a condition-specific safe speed for navigating the curve.

The final output is a consolidated set of both observed and inferred events, optimized for relevance and ready for transmission to the in-vehicle client.

3.5 Broker

The Broker acts as the communication hub between the platform and the in-vehicle clients. As a core component of the system, it manages and maintains client connections, receives Geo-Spatial Keys (GSKs) transmitted by the clients, and ensures that the corresponding sets of computed events are reliably routed back to the appropriate originating vehicles.

By handling message coordination and delivery, the broker enables timely, bidirectional communication between the edge and backend components of the hazard warning system.

4 Implementation Challenges

4.1 Backend and Event Generation

The first major implementation challenge lies in designing the warning system in a way that all data services are given enough time to process and respond to queries, while still ensuring that the complete set of events is returned within a bounded and practically acceptable timeframe - ideally close to real-time. This requires careful orchestration of asynchronous requests, efficient data retrieval and caching strategies, and robust timeout and fallback mechanisms to avoid delays caused by slower or temporarily unavailable data sources.

In our prototypical implementation, we integrated multiple data sources as separate services, each running independently within Docker containers. We currently use external weather data provided by a weather data provider, vehicle-related data such as crash events, traffic jams, and distracted driving behaviour obtained from a vehicle data marketplace, accident hotspot information supplied by a dedicated information provider, harsh braking data, and road geometry data, such as curvature, derived from historical driving records. All our services operate independently, so if one experiences delays or issues, the others remain unaffected, avoiding a monolithic architecture.

The event inference service running in a container queries all individual data services for events within a defined GSK (in our case currently a 4 km² area) and allocates each data service a finite amount of time to perform computations and return warning-relevant events to the in-vehicle client. Each data service currently has about 20 seconds time to answer a request, running in parallel, to answer the request while the event inference service has one second to complete its task.

Further, the event inference service merges multiple related events (the relatedness was determined by a domain expert capable in traffic risk estimation) such as curve data and weather data into a single, more meaningful event, a combination of curve and weather with safe curve speeds. This improves the significance and coherence of the warnings while reducing the number of events sent to the in-vehicle client.

Furthermore, we want to ensure that highly relevant information is not inadvertently filtered out, as this may impede the generation of future events.

For instance, weather data can serve as valuable contextual information for a wide range of event types or may even possess intrinsic significance on its own. Environmental conditions such as snow, ice, or heavy precipitation in a specific region can be treated as independent spatial events, enabling early warning mechanisms for drivers.

4.2 Frontend and Warning Mechanism

The second major implementation challenge lies in designing how data is accessed, processed, and transformed into actionable warning events that reach drivers in a timely manner. While drivers expect prompt alerts to react appropriately to potential hazards in near to real-time, the reality is that not all relevant data may be immediately available to generate such warnings. Additionally, low or unstable internet connectivity can further delay data transmission to the vehicle.

To address the challenge of timely and reliable driver warnings under variable connectivity and data availability, we implemented a two-step mechanism. Warning-relevant events are first generated on the server side using a Geo-Spatial Key (GSK), which defines a broader area of potential relevance. These events are then validated on the in-vehicle client using a driving corridor-based mechanism that focuses on the vehicle's real-time trajectory. This dual architecture is shown in figure 4 and balances data efficiency, connectivity limitations, and warning relevance.

In our prototypical implementation, the GSK is represented as a configurable square region (in our case currently a 4 km² area) surrounding the vehicle's current GPS position. The in-vehicle client sends a GSK to the server, which queries all relevant data

services for potential warning events in that area. Aggregated warning events are returned and cached locally on the in-vehicle client for low-latency access.

On the client side, a dynamic driving corridor is constructed as a triangle aligned with the vehicle's position, speed, and heading. This corridor is used to filter the cached events in real time. If a relevant event falls within this corridor, and certain local conditions are fulfilled (e.g. vehicle speed is above a threshold for a particular event), a warning is issued to the driver.

To ensure uninterrupted service, the in-vehicle client proactively requests data for the next GSK region before exiting the current one, allowing seamless preloading of warning events. Key parameters including GSK size, driving corridor geometry, and update intervals are configurable to support different operational scenarios and allow more frequent updates in high-risk areas, such as during evolving weather conditions or traffic incidents.

Fig. 4. GSK, Driving Corridor, Hazardous events and warnings

4.3 Frontend and Warning Mechanism

Getting access to data sources relevant for driver warning is very challenging. Hence, the third implementation challenge is how to effectively use currently available,

limited, and costly warning-relevant data to generate meaningful and actionable warning events for drivers. This must be achieved while minimizing data queries from data services to the data source, such as those for weather data or other vehicle data managed by third parties, to reduce costs, yet still ensure timely and relevant warning events are delivered to the vehicle.

In our prototypical implementation, weather information is collected from 100 spatially distributed data points across a defined driving region. The weather data service queries these points at hourly intervals, effectively treating each as a virtual weather station. Around each station, we define a square-shaped geographic zone that represents localized weather conditions such as precipitation, temperature, wind speed, visibility, and severe weather alerts. This structured spatial representation allows the system to associate real-time vehicle positions with nearby weather conditions for situational assessment.

In addition, our vehicle data service ingests real-time vehicle telemetry through a Kafka-based data stream, provided by a connected vehicle data marketplace. Each participating vehicle transmits relevant data, including position and risk-relevant events such as crash detections or the activation of vehicle safety systems like ABS or ESP. The incoming data stream is filtered and temporarily cached, making it readily available to the event inference service for enrichment, merging, or the generation of new hazard events based on driving behavior or incident detection.

In addition to leveraging external data sources, we also generated valuable datasets from historical vehicle trip data, including curve radius and braking information. Specifically, we derived curve data for the majority of curves within the same geographic region described above, based on trajectory data collected from past vehicle trips. This data is accessible via our dedicated curve data service and includes key attributes such as the curve radius and the maximum recommended safe speed under various road surface conditions - dry, wet, snowy, or icy. To estimate these safe speeds, we applied a heuristic formula based on the curve radius and a predefined safety margin. While effective as a baseline, this formula does not yet incorporate additional influencing factors such as road surface quality, gradient, or camber.

We also analyzed historical driving data to identify sudden braking events, clustering them to reveal brake hotspots—locations where drivers frequently decelerate. Similarly, we clustered historical accident data to define accident hotspots. Both are provided through dedicated data services and, along with the curve data service, support context-aware warnings by enriching the platform with locally derived insights.

4.4 Event Data Processing: Balancing between Server and Client

The fourth key implementation challenge is determining where specific parts of the data processing should take place, whether on the server or on the in-vehicle client, when deciding if a driver should be warned. Closely related is the question of how warning events should be structured and delivered. This requires careful coordination of which data is available at which point in the system and when. The system must be designed to be both performant and fault-tolerant, ensuring that warnings can still be generated even if certain data services are temporarily unavailable. Balancing the division of

labour between the platform and the client is essential for maintaining responsiveness, reliability, and overall system robustness.

To illustrate our implementation, we consider a concrete and typical warning scenario: alerting the driver when approaching a curvy curve too quickly during adverse weather conditions. The server queries weather data and curve data separately and combines weather data indicating rain with all curve data in the affected area, including their safety speed limits. It then adjusts the curve data by updating the recommended safe speeds to reflect the current weather conditions (e.g., lowering the speed due to rain). These updated curve data is sent as curve event to the in-vehicle client. The in-vehicle client continuously monitors the vehicle's speed and position. If the vehicle approaches such a curve within the driving corridor and is traveling faster than the computed safe speed for that curve and weather condition, it issues a warning to the driver. The following JSON code snippet defines such a curve event that has been enriched with weather data to provide both the original speed recommendations for various road conditions - dry, wet, snowy, and icy - and the currently recommended safe speed based on the prevailing weather. This merging of curve geometry and weather context (conducted by the Situational Inference and Event Computation Service) allows for a dynamic, situationally relevant warning to be generated for the driver.

Decision-making is distributed across components based on where the most accurate and relevant data resides. For instance, only the in-vehicle client has real-time access to the driver's position, speed, and internal vehicle signals. This allows it to locally infer higher-level events, such as hazardous driving conditions. In contrast, external data like weather can be processed independently, for example, flagging icy areas as standalone warnings.

```
{
  "gsk": { // GSK object structure },
  "status": "processed",
  "events": [
    {
      "eventID": 1,
      "eventDescription": "CURVE",
      "position": {
        "type": "Point",
        "coordinates": {
          "type": "Point",
          "coordFormat": "LongLat",
          "coordinates": [15.369951,
                        46.972921]
        }
      }
    },
    "eventDirection": 90.0,
    "eventTimestamp": 1625247600000,
    "speedLimits": {
      "speedDry": 80.0,
```

```
        "speedWet": 65.0,  
        "speedSnow": 45.0,  
        "speedIce": 25.0,  
        "speedSafe": 70.0,  
    }  
}  
]  
}
```

Fig. 5. GSK Object Structure

4.5 Warning Logics Design

There are many types of meaningful warnings that can, in principle, be implemented using existing data sources - ranging from infrastructure and weather data to real-time vehicle telemetry - as well as new sources that may emerge in the future. The fifth key implementation challenge lies in how to translate these diverse data points into effective warnings: that is, how to design warning logics that transform raw data into meaningful, actionable alerts for drivers. This requires the development of robust methods and algorithms capable of interpreting heterogeneous input data and triggering clear, context-aware messages that enhance driver awareness and safety without causing overload or false alarms.

In our prototypical implementation, we deliberately focused on relatively simple warning logics to validate the system's core functionality. We propose a structured design approach in which experts initially create "warning stories" on paper by defining fictional but plausible hazardous events at specific road locations - such as the presence of distracted drivers or high-risk intersections - where issuing a warning would be meaningful. These warning stories serve as a foundation for designing and testing alert logic and can be evaluated in both real-world and simulated driving scenarios.

For example, we implemented a warning for drivers approaching a tight curve too fast under adverse weather conditions. This logic merges static road geometry (e.g., curve radius and location) with dynamic weather data (e.g., rain, snow) and real-time vehicle speed to determine whether a warning should be issued. Similarly, we have implemented general weather-based alerts, such as warnings for icy road segments, based on geographic weather overlays. The warning logic in the curve scenario, for instance, is: a curve becomes dangerous when it is tight, the road is wet, and the driver is approaching it at a speed above the adjusted safety threshold. This kind of logic - though straightforward - demonstrates how combining different types of data can result in context-aware, situationally relevant warnings.

If there is additional information about previous accidents at a specific location, the risk level can be classified as significantly higher. Furthermore, if real-time data from other vehicles indicates active risk-related events - such as driver distraction, ESP (Electronic Stability Program) activation, or even an ongoing accident in the curve - the warning becomes even more critical. However, even the combination of the curve event with just a single additional risk signal may suffice to classify the curve as hazardous.

This illustrates the central implementation challenge: the hazard event logic must be designed with enough flexibility to incorporate a broad and dynamic range of input signals, including both historical and real-time data, without relying on a fixed rule set.

At the same time, the system must also be capable of generating meaningful warnings even in the absence of extensive supplementary data—relying, for example, solely on curve geometry or weather conditions—while maintaining a high degree of precision and relevance. Importantly, the logic must be robust against false positives: it should never generate warnings where no potential hazard exists, as such “hallucinated” alerts would undermine driver trust and reduce system effectiveness. This trade-off between richness and robustness demands a careful, data-aware design of the event fusion and decision logic, supported by heuristics and expert knowledge () that can weigh available signals and their combinations to determine the appropriate level of urgency and whether a warning is necessary.

4.6 Data and Event Invalidation

The sixth major key implementation challenge is the handling of data and event invalidation. Not all safety-relevant data remains valid indefinitely: Weather conditions evolve, distraction events are transient, and incidents such as accidents or roadworks have limited temporal and spatial relevance. The system must therefore continuously assess the validity period of each event and ensure that outdated or no longer applicable information is removed or updated in a timely manner to avoid misleading or unnecessary warnings.

In our current prototype, many events span the full duration of the evaluation period and are derived from historical datasets, explicit deletion or expiration has not been required. However, for few dynamic data types such as weather and vehicle-related events, we have implemented basic invalidation strategies. Weather data is refreshed hourly, while vehicle-related events are streamed continuously. Events from the vehicle stream are cached in a database for the data service and invalidated after a maximum of two hours, ensuring that only recent, potentially relevant incidents are retained for warning evaluation.

As the platform scales, handling more data sources or time-sensitive use cases like real-time driver distraction detection, effective data and event invalidation becomes crucial. One approach is to timestamp all events and assign a type-specific validity period after which it’s excluded from processing. While simple in concept, choosing appropriate expiration intervals is challenging. For instance, a distraction alert may be valid for seconds, weather data for up to an hour, while events like road construction lack predictable durations, requiring adaptive or manual invalidation strategies.

4.7 Human Factor: Vehicle integration and warning modality

The seventh and final key implementation challenge is how to integrate the warning mechanism into the vehicle in a way that does not distract the driver. The system must alert drivers to hazards while minimizing cognitive load and avoiding any increase in distraction.

This challenge involves deciding whether to use a mounted smartphone or integrate the system into the in-vehicle infotainment system, as well as determining the most effective modality for delivering warnings, visual, acoustic, haptic, or a combination. The challenge lies in striking a balance between providing timely and relevant information and ensuring the warning mechanism remains subtle and non-intrusive, so that it genuinely improves safety rather than undermines it.

For simplicity, our prototype uses a smartphone as the in-vehicle client, displaying visual warnings via an on-screen triangle and brief message. We also explored integration as an Android Automotive OS (AAOS) app to show alerts within the infotainment system. To reduce distraction, we furthermore considered alternative modalities like ambient lighting, haptic feedback (e.g., steering wheel vibrations), or audio cues, leveraging in-vehicle actuators for more intuitive driver alerts.

5 Hazard Warning System Prototype and Discussion

5.1 System Prototype

In this paper, we introduce hazard warning systems as a specific category of driver assistance systems. We present our architectural and procedural approach and discuss the implementation challenges encountered, along with the solutions applied in our prototypical system. The preceding sections have already outlined key design and implementation decisions. Building on this foundation, this section introduces the developed system prototype in more detail and highlights how the individual components interact to enable data-driven hazard detection and warning generation.

The Hazard Warning System Prototype was implemented as a client-server application. The client is realized as a progressive web application (PWA) that continuously queries the backend server using its current location, represented as a Geo-Spatial Key (GSK). This spatial abstraction enables efficient querying and filtering of relevant events within a defined geographic context. Based on this query, the client retrieves warning-relevant events and evaluates, in a lightweight decision layer, whether a warning should be issued to the driver. This separation of concerns allows computationally intensive data aggregation and preprocessing to remain on the server side, while latency-sensitive decision-making can be performed closer to the user.

On the server side, the system aggregates data from multiple connected services to identify potentially hazardous situations. The server compiles a list of relevant events, enriched with contextual information such as temporal validity, severity, and spatial relevance, and transmits this information to the client. The currently integrated services include a weather service based on data from the Austrian provider UBIMET, accessed via a REST API, which supplies environmental conditions; an accident hotspot service identifying high-risk locations; a curve analysis service assessing whether a vehicle is approaching a curve at an unsafe speed under current conditions; and a connected vehicle service from the German data marketplace CARUSO, integrated via a Kafka stream, providing information on distracted driving behavior and reported vehicle

accidents. The integration of heterogeneous data sources enables a more comprehensive and context-aware representation of potential hazards along the driving route.

The server infrastructure is implemented as a containerized environment using Docker, where each service operates within its own isolated container. This design ensures modularity, enabling independent deployment, maintenance, and scalability of individual services. Furthermore, as the integrated services exhibit varying response times and data update frequencies, this architecture prevents blocking effects between services and supports asynchronous data processing. It also improves overall system robustness and resilience, as individual services can fail or be updated without compromising the entire system. Additionally, the modular design facilitates the seamless replacement, extension, or integration of new data providers, which is particularly important in evolving data ecosystems where new mobility data sources continuously emerge.

Overall, this architecture supports a flexible and extensible hazard warning system that can adapt to changing data availability and evolving application requirements, while maintaining responsiveness and scalability in real-world deployment scenarios.

Fig. 6. Client-Server Architecture

The client application was developed as a progressive web application (PWA) using the shinyMobile framework in R, a programming language and environment for statistical computing and data-driven application development. This approach proved particularly suitable for rapid prototyping and iterative development, allowing for the fast integration and testing of different warning strategies and data sources. Furthermore, the use of a PWA enables cross-platform deployment, ensuring accessibility across a wide range of mobile devices without requiring platform-specific implementations.

In addition, a web-based dashboard was developed using the React framework to support system monitoring and testing. The dashboard enables the visualization of events within a defined geographic region and allows users to manually add or remove

events. This functionality is primarily intended for testing and validation purposes, facilitating controlled scenario creation and systematic analysis of system behavior. In particular, it supports the simulation of hazard scenarios and enables developers to evaluate the impact of different event types, data qualities, and configurations on the warning logic.

Figure 7 illustrates two screenshots of the driver warning dashboard implemented within the PWA. The first screenshot shows the system state when no warnings are active, reflecting normal driving conditions without relevant hazards detected in the driving corridor. The second screenshot presents an active monitoring scenario, including the vehicle position (blue marker at the center), the Geo-Spatial Key (GSK) represented as a green rectangular area, and the driving corridor visualized as a blue trapezoidal shape. Additionally, markers indicate accident-prone locations (cross symbols), as well as a marker representing a detected vehicle crash.

Warnings are generated dynamically based on a combination of vehicle speed, environmental conditions, and the number and classification of events detected within the defined driving corridor. This context-aware approach allows the system to prioritize relevant hazards and adapt warning behavior to the current driving situation, thereby reducing unnecessary alerts and supporting more effective driver assistance.

Fig. 7. Screenshot of driver warning dashboard (progressive web app)

5.2 Limitations and Discussion

We conducted multiple test drives on different road types to evaluate the usefulness and practical applicability of the developed system under varying real-world conditions. These tests provided initial insights into system behavior, responsiveness, and the relevance of generated warnings in realistic driving scenarios. In particular, they allowed us to observe how the system reacts to dynamic changes in driving context, such as variations in speed, road geometry, and environmental conditions.

For example, one evaluation drive was conducted on a rural road in the greater Graz area, offering a variety of potentially hazardous situations, including sharp curves, simulated crash events, and simulated distracted driving scenarios to test the warning mechanisms (cf. Figure 8). During this test, the system demonstrated robust performance, consistently identifying relevant events and generating timely warnings. The usefulness of context-aware hazard warnings became evident to the driver, particularly in situations where hazards were not immediately visible or predictable.

Fig. 8. Application in use during an evaluation drive, displaying an active hazard warning.

These observations further motivate continued system development, particularly with regard to improving the user interface and transitioning toward a more professional and integrated solution. Future iterations should focus on enhanced usability, more intuitive interaction and alert mechanisms, and tighter integration into the driving environment, for instance by embedding the application into the vehicle's infotainment system. Moreover, more systematic and large-scale evaluations will be necessary to validate the effectiveness and user acceptance of the system under diverse conditions.

In addition, these findings motivate the integration of additional data sources, including potentially commercial data services, to enhance coverage, improve data quality, and increase the likelihood of detecting and issuing relevant hazard warnings.

At the same time, we acknowledge several limitations of our approach. The presented hazard warning system is a prototype and not a fully operational solution with guaranteed service availability or formal service-level agreements. As such, the system may exhibit variability in performance depending on network connectivity, data availability, and the responsiveness of integrated external services. Furthermore, the current implementation is primarily intended for proof-of-concept validation and does not yet meet the robustness, reliability, and integration standards required for deployment in production-grade or safety-critical environments.

Another unresolved challenge involves operation in long tunnels and regions with limited or no internet connectivity, where the absence of a stable connection can lead to update failures or delayed hazard detection. Additionally, larger update areas, represented by Geo-Spatial Keys (GSKs), introduce unnecessary computational overhead for managing cached events, increase data transfer demands, and lead to longer update intervals. This, in turn, reduces the accuracy and timeliness of soft real-time warnings. A potential mitigation strategy is the use of route prediction, similar to modern navigation systems, which would allow preloading of relevant historical hazard events along the anticipated driving path and thereby reduce reliance on continuous connectivity.

Consequently, the warning system is not designed to function as a safety-critical component on which drivers can rely under all circumstances. Instead, it should be understood as a driver assistance or comfort feature. This limitation arises from several factors, including the potential unavailability of data sources, intermittent connectivity, and broader infrastructure constraints.

Furthermore, accessing and licensing data from diverse sources, if available at all, remains a costly endeavor. This is largely due to the high volume of API requests and continuous data streaming required to support a large number of connected vehicles and near real-time warning capabilities. The cost implications of such data consumption represent a significant barrier to large-scale deployment, particularly when integrating multiple data providers or scaling across fleets and vehicle brands.

Privacy is a key concern in connected vehicle systems (Cichy et al., 2021), as the system processes vehicle position data that could reveal individual movement patterns, as well as speed information that may be sensitive in regulatory or legal contexts. To address these concerns, the system follows a privacy-by-design approach. The in-vehicle client transmits only a generalized Geo-Spatial Key (GSK) instead of precise coordinates, and no speed or direction data is sent to the backend. GSKs are cached only temporarily and are not stored persistently. All processing related to speed and direction is performed locally within the vehicle and is used exclusively for evaluating warning conditions. This design minimizes the transmission of personally identifiable information and ensures that sensitive data remains within the vehicle, aligning with established data minimization principles.

6 Conclusion and Outlook

In conclusion, we presented the conceptual architecture and workflow of a data-driven, in-vehicle hazard warning system. Based on our prototype, we highlighted key implementation challenges—ranging from data acquisition and integration to real-time processing, warning logic, and client-side evaluation. These insights can guide researchers developing similar systems and offer practical relevance for industry stakeholders like automotive OEMs and Tier-1 suppliers exploring contextual, data-driven hazard warnings. Unlike many commercial solutions currently limited to static event reporting, such as traffic jams or accidents, as delivered by routing providers, our approach demonstrates how dynamic, situationally enriched warnings can enhance driver awareness and contribute to road safety in a more nuanced and adaptive way.

Future research can focus on implementing warning systems that operate closer to real time, enhancing both the responsiveness and relevance of alerts. Additionally, improving in-vehicle integration—such as delivering warnings via the instrument cluster or head-up display—can help adapt warning modalities to individual user needs and driving contexts. Another important direction is conducting more extensive user studies to gather structured feedback on technology acceptance, usability, and perceived usefulness, helping refine system design and increase adoption.

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References

1. Bengler, K., Dietmayer, K., Farber, B., Maurer, M., Stiller, C., Winner, H.: Three decades of driver assistance systems: Review and future perspectives. *IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Magazine* 6(4), 6–22 (2014)
2. Bergel-Hayat, R., Debarh, M., Antoniou, C., Yannis, G.: Explaining the road accident risk: Weather effects. *Accident Analysis & Prevention* 60, 456–465 (2013)
3. Bogenreif, C., Souleyrette, R.R., Hans, Z.: Identifying and measuring horizontal curves and related effects on highway safety. *Journal of Transportation Safety & Security* 4(3), 179–192 (2012)
4. Chen, W., Wang, W., Wang, K., Li, Z., Li, H., Liu, S.: Lane departure warning systems and lane line detection methods based on image processing and semantic segmentation: A review. *Journal of Traffic and Transportation Engineering (English Edition)* 7(6), 748–774 (2020)
5. Cichy, P., Salge, T. O., & Kohli, R.: Privacy concerns and data sharing in the internet of things: Mixed methods evidence from connected cars. *MIS quarterly*, 45(4), 1863–1891. (2021)
6. Dantas, A., Fowler, M., Koorey, G.: Effect of road network bendiness on traffic crash occurrence. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological* 117, 101–116 (2018)

7. Ebinger, N., Neuhuber, N., Moser, J., Trösterer, S., Stocker, A.: Which partially automated driving function do drivers prefer? Results from two field studies on public highways. *Transportation Engineering* 17, 100236 (2024)
8. European Commission: Vehicle safety and automated/connected vehicles. https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/automotive-industry/vehicle-safety-and-automated-connected-vehicles_en, last accessed 2025/06/30
9. Intini, P., Colonna, P., Ryeng, E.O.: Route familiarity in road safety: A literature review and an identification proposal. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour* 62, 651–671 (2019)
10. Jonah, B.A.: Accident risk and risk-taking behaviour among young drivers. *Accident Analysis & Prevention* 18(4), 255–271 (1986)
11. Jamson, A.H., Lai, F.C., Carsten, O.M.: Potential benefits of an adaptive forward collision warning system. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies* 16(4), 471–484 (2008)
12. Kaiser, C., Stocker, A., Festl, A., Lechner, G., Fellmann, M.: A research agenda for vehicle information systems, *European Conference on Information Systems – ECIS* (2018)
13. Kaiser, C., Festl, A., Pucher, G., Fellmann, M., Stocker, A.: The vehicle data value chain as a lightweight model to describe digital vehicle services. In: *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Web Information Systems and Technologies (WEBIST)*, pp. 68–79 (2019)
14. Kaiser, C., Stocker, A., Festl, A., Djokic-Petrovic, M., Papatheocharous, E., Wallberg, A., Fellmann, M.: A vehicle telematics service for driving style detection: Implementation and privacy challenges. In: *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Vehicle Technology and Intelligent Transport Systems (VEHITS)*, pp. 29–36 (2020)
15. Kaiser, C., Stocker, A., Viscusi, G., Fellmann, M., Richter, A.: Conceptualising value creation in data-driven services: The case of vehicle data. *International Journal of Information Management* 59, 102335 (2021)
16. Karlaftis, M.G., Golias, I.: Effects of road geometry and traffic volumes on rural roadway accident rates. *Accident Analysis & Prevention* 34(3), 357–365 (2002)
17. Kashevnik, A., Shchedrin, R., Kaiser, C., Stocker, A.: Driver distraction detection methods: A literature review and framework. *IEEE Access* 9, 60063–60076 (2021)
18. Liu, G., Wang, L., Zou, S.: A radar-based blind spot detection and warning system for driver assistance. In: *2017 IEEE 2nd Advanced Information Technology, Electronic and Automation Control Conference (IAEAC)*, pp. 2204–2208. IEEE (2017)
19. Malin, F., Norros, I., Innamaa, S.: Accident risk of road and weather conditions on different road types. *Accident Analysis & Prevention* 122, 181–188 (2019)
20. Maze, T.H., Agarwal, M., Burchett, G.: Whether weather matters to traffic demand, traffic safety, and traffic operations and flow. *Transportation Research Record* 1948(1), 170–176 (2006)
21. McCarty, D., Kim, H.W.: Risky behaviors and road safety: An exploration of age and gender influences on road accident rates. *PLoS ONE* 19(1), e0296663 (2024)
22. Möller, F., Jussen, I., Springer, V., Gieß, A., Schweihoff, J.C., Gelhaar, J., Guggenberger, T., Otto, B.: Industrial data ecosystems and data spaces. *Electronic Markets* 34(1), 41 (2024)
23. Nischak, F., Hanelt, A.: Ecosystem change in the era of digital innovation – A longitudinal analysis and visualization of the automotive ecosystem. In: *Proceedings of the International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS)* (2019)
24. Parker, D., Reason, J.T., Manstead, A.S., Stradling, S.G.: Driving errors, driving violations and accident involvement. *Ergonomics* 38(5), 1036–1048 (1995)

25. Osafune, T., Takahashi, T., Kiyama, N., Sobue, T., Yamaguchi, H., Higashino, T.: Analysis of accident risks from driving behaviors. *International Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems Research* 15, 192–202 (2017)
26. Otto, S., Wlcek, M., Wortmann, F.: Towards conceptualizing software-defined vehicles: A systematic review and future research avenues. In: *Proceedings of the European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS) (2025)*
27. Regan, M.A., Hallett, C., Gordon, C.P.: Driver distraction and driver inattention: Definition, relationship and taxonomy. *Accident Analysis & Prevention* 43(5), 1771–1781 (2011)
28. Rengarasu, T.M., Hagiwara, T., Hirasawa, M.: Effects of road geometry and cross-section variables on traffic accidents: Study using homogeneous road segments. *Transportation Research Record* 2102(1), 34–42 (2009)
29. Ryder, B., Gahr, B., Dahlinger, A.: An in-vehicle information system providing accident hotspot warnings. In: *Proceedings of the 24th European Conference on Information Systems – ECIS (2016)*
30. Sagberg, F., Selpi, Bianchi Piccinini, G.F., Engström, J.: A review of research on driving styles and road safety. *Human Factors* 57(7), 1248–1275 (2015)
31. Schömig, N., Metz, B.: Three levels of situation awareness in driving with secondary tasks. *Safety Science* 56, 44–51 (2013)
32. Sterk, F., Stocker, A., Heinz, D., Weinhardt, C.: Unlocking the value from car data: A taxonomy and archetypes of connected car business models. *Electronic Markets* 34(1), 13 (2024)
33. Stocker, A., Kaiser, C., Fellmann, M.: Quantified vehicles: Novel services for vehicle lifecycle data. *Business & Information Systems Engineering* 59, 125–130 (2017)
34. Stocker, A., Kaiser, C., Lechner, G., Fellmann, M.: A conceptual framework for mobility data science. *IEEE Access* 12, 117126–117142 (2024)
35. Stocker, A., Musser, M.: From data to warnings: Challenges in building in-vehicle data-driven hazard warning systems. In: *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Web Information Systems and Technologies (WEBIST)*, pp. 236–243. *SciTePress* (2025)
36. Stocker, A.: User archetypes of physical AI systems: Insights from an automated driving systems study. In: *Proceedings of the European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS 2025) (2025)*
37. Stocker, A., Richter, A., Ebinger, N.: Feature-specific trust calibration in physical AI systems. In: *Proceedings of the International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS 2025) (2025)*
38. Theofilatos, A.: Incorporating real-time traffic and weather data to explore road accident likelihood and severity in urban arterials. *Journal of Safety Research* 61, 9–21 (2017)
39. Trager, J., Kalová, L., Pagany, R., Dorner, W.: Warning apps for road safety: A technological and economical perspective for autonomous driving. *International Journal of Human–Computer Interaction* 37(4), 363–377 (2021)
40. Turner, S., Tate, F.N.: Relationship between road geometry, observed travel speed and rural accidents. *NZ Transport Agency, Wellington* (2009)
41. Xu, J., Bowers, A.R.: Hazard warning modalities and timing thresholds for older drivers with impaired vision. *Accident Analysis & Prevention* 202, 107 (2024)
42. Young, K., Regan, M.: Driver distraction: A review of the literature. In: Faulks, I.J., Regan, M., Stevenson, M., Brown, J., Porter, A., Irwin, J.D. (eds.) *Distracted Driving*, pp. 379–405. *Australasian College of Road Safety, Sydney* (2007)
43. Zambetti, M., Adrodegari, F., Pezzotta, G., Pinto, R., Rapaccini, M., Barbieri, C.: From data to value: Conceptualising data-driven product service systems. *Production Planning & Control* 34(2), 207–223 (2023)